

" Baburnoma" historical figures mental image

Abstract: This article focuses on the analysis of the image of creators and rulers depicted in "Boburnoma" by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur. The work explores issues such as historicity and artistic interpretation, the author's skill in creating a literary portrait of a historical person.

Key words: Babur, "Boburnoma", creative person, image of the ruler, historical fact, artistic interpretation.

After Alisher Navoi, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur is a writer who became famous in the history of Uzbek classical literature by creating prose works, ghazals of dillrabo, qita, rubai, and masnavi. Especially, his work "Boburnoma" is translated and read in 32 countries of the world today. The simple narration of the author of the work, the realistic expression of historical events, as the author noted, "For the purpose of this history, let the truth of every word be known and the facts of every case be edited ¹." The assessment of all the historical figures mentioned in the work, facts, events, proofs prove that they are true.

Interest in "Boburnoma" began during Babur's lifetime, the work was translated into Persian, then English scholars Lane Poole, Monstewart Elphinstone, Edward Dawson, Mrs. Anetta Beveridge, her husband Henry Beveridge and others not only brought Babur's work to English readers, but also analyzed it. with the help of dictionaries, they tried to make the work readable and understandable to the students.

Uzbek scientists also made a great contribution to the study of Babur's work. Ya. Gulomov, H. Yakubov, V. Zohidov, S. Azimjonova, S. Jalilov, P. Shamsiev, S. Mirzaev, B. Valikho'jaev, A. Hayitmetov, G. Salomov, H. Nazarova, H. Quadratullaev, N. Komilov, S. Hasanov, N. Otajonov, A. Ibrohimov, I. Hakkulov, Z. Kholmanova among writers, Oybek, P. Kadirov, B. Boyqabilov, Kh. Sulstonov, A. Eshonov are among them.

After independence, it was important to comprehensively research Babur's work, to give a wide place to the issues of his artistic skills. In particular, in the scientific works of scientists such as A. Qayumov, A. Hayitmetov, A. Abdurashidov, I. Hakkulov, H. Quadratullaev, A. Ibrohimov, I. Sulaymonov, some aspects of the human psyche were studied in "Boburnoma".

Among the complex political and social processes from the end of the 15th century to the 30s of the 16th century, the struggle for the throne between the successors of Amir Temur continued violently, and sometimes one or another Timurizade took the throne at the top of the kingdom, as a result of which today the armies belonging to one sultan are crowned by another. joining the ranks and entering the battle made the management of the kingdom in the political arena much more complicated. As a historical, autobiographical, scientific work, "Boburnoma" describes this complex process through historical events, the struggle for power, the frequent changes in the mental state of rulers, begs, and visionaries, the history of ownership and distribution of property, its consequences, and deep conspiracies. and we witness it described in a comprehensive, analytical manner.

"Boburnoma" is literally a spiritual and psychological source. It depicts the history of Movarounnahr, Khurasan and India, the lifestyle of the crown princes of the three regions and

¹Boburnoma . To the publication preparer S. Hasanov . Tashkent . East . 2002. 201 p. In the following examples taken from this work, the page of the work is indicated.

the nobles around them, the lifestyle of their women, ordinary soldiers, poets and artisans, and the mental state of people related to the spiritual life of the time are described in connection with the most complex processes. Foreign and Uzbek scholars have also emphasized this feature of the work. For example, English historian Leigh Poole, who was seriously engaged in Babur's work, writes: "Babur's memoirs are not a simple diary of a soldier's military campaigns and retreats; In these memoirs, personal impressions and subtle thoughts about the world are given by the owner of an impressive heart who knows Eastern literature very well, is a sensitive and knowledgeable observer, who carefully studies people, who can think about them objectively and justly ². " Or let's look at the opinion of the English orientalist Monstuart Elphinstone: "In these memoirs, the life of the great Turkish king is described in detail, his personal feelings are free from any exaggeration and veiling. His style is simple and manly, as well as lively and imaginative. He describes the faces, traditions, aspirations, actions of his contemporaries as clearly as a mirror... But the bright character of the author gives the work the most charm» ³.

If we draw a conclusion based on the opinions of foreign and Uzbek scientists, based on the variety of artistic images in "Boburnoma", the description of the person's character and mental state in the depiction of historical figures, it is necessary to consider the victory and defeat, which is a typical situation in the life of the people of the time, in the context of the spiritual and psychological process. After all, historical events in "Boburnoma" were able to show themselves clearly in this aspect. In no other period have historical events changed so rapidly as in the end of the 15th century and the 30s of the 16th century. While describing the events of the same period in "Boburnoma", typological processes in the position and character of contemporary people are revealed before our eyes. This process alternates with the reality of time and space, bravery and cowardice on the battlefield, valor and betrayal, the joy of victory and the pain of defeat, especially in the depiction of winners and losers. Determining complex situations in the psyche of a historical person, observing and explaining changes in it is evidence of Babur's high skill. In the work, the changes in the mentality of not only the ruler, but also the common man, sometimes the triumphant celebration of victory or the bitter pain of defeat, or even the change in the fate of a person, is an extraordinary situation, which is described by Babur with a unique skill.

The rapid exchange of events, the strength of dynamism, the sudden change of the mental and psychological process, and the impact on the psyche of individuals are skillfully described by the author of the work. Babur, the winner on the battlefield, soon becomes a loser, and again due to conflicts, he triumphs and becomes the winner. This change occurs several times almost from the beginning to the end of the work.

Evolutions in the psyche of a historical figure occur in the mental state of Shaibani Khan, Husayn Boygaro, Khusravshah, Baqi Chaganiyoni, Kasimbek, Shahbegim, Ibrahim Lo'di and others as well as the author of the work. In the artistic reflection of the mental state of a historical person, we come across such images as the high psychology of the writer, the sudden spiritual change in the natural character and character, the fading of the signs of life and, on the contrary, the rebirth, which are important because of the artistic interpretation by the author.

² Lane Poole. Babur. Oxford. 1899. S. 9.

³ Singh N.K. Banerjee A.U. History India. M., 1954. S. 214.

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